

An Exploration of Motherhood in the Fiction of Anita Desai

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Abstract

This paper seeks to explore the realm of Indian motherhood within the fiction of Anita Desai and Indian Literature in English in general, and present the complicated ideologies and histories that inform its position. Anita Myles states “The novelist (Desai) makes it clear that there is no simple, straight forwards solution to the dilemma of woman. It is the awakening of her consciousness which imparts the required strength to conquer the bastion of male dominance” (60).

Keywords: Feminism, Post colonialism, Motherhood

In his essay “Women Writing About Women: Feminist Perspectives in Indian Women’s Novel in English,” Santosh Gupta describes the history of Indian women’s writing in English, which emerged in the nineteenth century after it was introduced “into the antahpurus of some aristocratic liberal Indians” (73). He goes on to state that in the twentieth century, Indian women writing in English explored a women’s world “that was beginning to be influenced by the emergence of educated self-conscious women....Woman’s relation with the new society generated in the consciousness of the changing milieu which is reflected in the writing of this period,” of which most is characterized as belonging to the literary genre of social realism (80)

1) Social realism is defined in the Oxford English Dictionary as “The realistic depiction of contemporary (esp. working-class) life as a means of social or political comment,” and this form was used by many Indian novelists during the time of the Independence Movement¹ as a means to dispel inaccurate portrayals of India, especially in terms of its colonial past, and also to raise awareness of significant issues such as communalism, dowry murders, and caste violence in the Western world. Anita Desai does draw on this tradition some, and as Santosh Gupta relates, there is commonality between her novels and the novels of Nayantara Sahgal, both “portray the acute sense of entrapment and suffering of women in the upper and lower middle classes” (85). Literary critic Dhawan says that Anita Desai as a writer outside of this movement, though, stating that she

ushered in a new era of psychological realism in this genre [referring to Indo- Anglian fiction] with her novel Cry, the

Peacock in 1963. Her novels are materially different from those of other eminent Indian women novelists writing in English, such as Kamala Markandaya, Ruth Praver Jhabvala and Nayantara Sahgal who concern themselves mainly with social and political themes of the East-West encounter. Anita Desai's serious concern is with 'the journey within' of her characters, the chief protagonists being female characters. (12)

Although Anita Desai emerged as a writer during a time period when female Indian writers were actively exploring this genre of social realism, her fiction clearly belongs to a different realm, the realm of modernism. Desai's preoccupation with the inner psychic distress of her main characters and their personal struggles to define and assert an individual identity yields itself more easily to a modernist novel construction. Scholar Brajesh Kumar agrees with this assertion and claims that "among these eminent Indian women novelists writing novels in English, Anita Desai is one, who is more interested in the interior landscape of the mind rather than in politics or socio-political realities" (65). Writing in a prescribed format, she would not be able to explore the mythical aspects of Indian femininity while simultaneously exploring entirely individual responses to specific incidents, thereby increasing the complexity of her female characters and reducing the risk of homogenization and essentialist representations.

Desai has often commented that she has been greatly influenced by the works of Virginia Woolf and Russian writers such as Fyodor Dostoevsky, and it is clear after reading her novels that this is unquestionably the case. Her style and investigation of feminine sensibility is reminiscent of that in Woolf's *To the Lighthouse*, among other works. Asha Kanwar notes the similarities between the two authors in her essay "Anita Desai and Virginia Woolf: A Comparative Study," clearly identifying both authors' preoccupation with the way time, memory, and nostalgia operate over a long time period, changing histories and changing the perceptions of the people involved. Kanwar notes similarities in both novelists' works:

there is a constant shift from past to present to future. The past is defined in terms of human memories and the future in terms of human expectations. There is an underlying strain of longing for the past, of nostalgia....It informs not only the content of their work, but shapes the structure as well. For it posits two different times – the present and a longed-for past, upon which the whole novel can be built....we find almost obsessive involvement with the character's past as a key to their consciousness, their life. A preoccupation with Nostalgia and Memory thus becomes an integral part of their craft. (11, 20)

As is the case in Virginia Woolf's famous work *A Room of One's Own*, female characters in Desai's novels similarly search for an independent identity and place to call their own, a place safe from patriarchal intervention and male domination. Desai's use of narrative voice and her investigation of the psyches of her female characters allow for further insight into her protagonists and also question what constitutes identity and what identity means for different women. Kanwar's delineation of Woolf's goals as a novelist compared with Desai's and says "the exploration of the human personality so as to attain a vision of life's meaning. Her characters live, think and unfold in time and hence her preoccupation underlies her concern with the phenomena of memory, change and death and drives her to ask several different questions" (15).

In Anita Desai's short article "A Secret Connivance" (1990), she states, "If literature, if art has any purpose then it is to show one, bravely and uncompromisingly, the plain face of truth, and here in the West, just as in the East, we must learn to distinguish and recognize, and to value. Once you have told the truth, you have broken free of society, of its prisons. You have entered the realm of freedom" (976).

This point made by Desai in regards to her fiction writing encapsulates her artistic intent in literature: to portray truthfully and realistically complex characters that transcend stereotypes

or simplistic images. Although she declares that she is not interested in social and political commentary, her honest characterizations of both men and women allow numerous insights into authentic Indian experiences and opens space for scholarly criticism and debate. Most critics focus upon her depictions of Indian women, using her multi-dimensional female characters to challenge typical representations of Indian women in literature that commonly either evokes the mythical woman or the eternal oppressed victim. In contrast, her fiction makes a new space in which Indian women might explore selfhood, and she does not place any limits or constraints on how that identity can be discovered. In order to map the daily realities of Indian women, and to investigate the developments of the autonomous female self as depicted in fiction, a critic must look at novels that show the heterogeneity of Indian women's experiences and explore what those experiences foreground. Anita Desai's novels offer a variety of female characters that span the entire spectrum of Indian femininity, and through the various characters she investigates feminine sensibility and the female psyche. Desai has been a writer for over thirty years, and so her novels also span decades, easily illustrating how Indian gendered self-identity has changed and developed over time in response to a variety of native and foreign factors. It is clear through both Desai's fiction and her comments on the subject that she is interested in breaking down stereotypical representations, whether these are of Indian women, Indian mothers, or India in general, and she challenges her readers to do the same. In "A Secret Connivance," for instance, she states that the West

has two fixed notions about India. One is that it is a romantic land, full of holy men, maharajas, palaces and elephants: the other is of India as a land of horrors – a place of intolerable poverty and squalor, hunger and disease. How can one country have two such contradictory images? The reason is that neither is true – each is only a half-truth. You may have been made familiar with the face of the maharaja and the face of the beggar child, but have you learnt anything of the human being within? (976)

This question she asks the readers, and Western readers in particular, is indicative of what she is exploring in her novels, how stereotypical representations inform depictions and perceptions of people and why those stereotypes need to be revealed, explored, and broken down. In order to understand Indian mothers, one needs to note the variety of circumstances and experiences that affect and shape each individual person without resorting to a formulaic illustration imposed onto an entire community, nation, or gender.

Specifically, this paper focuses on Anita Desai's concern with the way mythical and ideological representations of Indian women contort and make the image of motherhood and maternity prescriptive within the context of her novels and, of course, in the larger Indian society. Figures such as Sita and the mother goddess constrain Indian women in two explicit ways, since they imply that every woman should be a mother but at the same time present an ideal which no woman can attain. In "Mapping Motherhood: The Fiction of Anita Desai," literary critic Geetanjali Chanda notes that Desai often "weaves the traditional duality of the mother as creator and destroyer and embeds the text in an Indian reality where actual mothers are often ignored or ill-treated; whereas in folklore, myth and nation building the idea of motherhood is venerated and iconic mothers are worshipped" (75). Critic Radha Chakravarty agrees and adds that "in India, women's self-worth and value are usually dependent on their reproductive functions. This valorization of motherhood has its own built-in paradoxes: maternity is associated with a capacity for voluntary self-sacrifice which entitles the mother to her quasi-divine status" (77).

Although there is much about Desai's fiction that lends itself easily to the exploration of the female psyche and the effects the Indian social order has upon Indian mothers, her exploration is not necessarily a complete picture of Indian women. Desai often focuses on middle – to upper-class women, which is clearly not representative of even half of India's population, a fact one should

keep in mind while reading her work. Some critics have criticized Desai for this elitism, but as she states in “A Secret Connivance,” her purpose is to portray honestly unique characters, and since her background is unmistakably middle – to upper-class, it makes sense that she wishes only to depict the experiences and psychological workings of this specific, familiar class group. Although Anita Desai does portray a limited class, she does not fall into the trap of essentializing Indian women, or mothers in particular, vividly illustrating instead the variety of complexities and intricacies through her female characters and their search for their own authentic sense of Indian motherhood and also their own sense of authentic self.

Another qualifier often made by critics of Anita Desai is that she is writing about India in a novel format explicitly not the social realist novel and, further, in English. If she writes in the style and for the purposes often ascribed to Nayantara Sahgal or Kamala Markandaya in English, they argue, her work would make more sense since the purpose of the social realist novel has often been to raise the consciousness of the Western world and to represent the actual reality of Indian life, but to write in English about the deep, complicated realms of the psyches of Indian upper-class characters appears to cater to a specific readership in India and, in essence, to negate much of Indian life. Although English fluency is greatly on the rise in India, Desai’s novels will be most read by the Indian elite, the educated middle and upper classes. Indian critics also add that on top of the limited readership within India, English itself is too easily associated with India’s colonial past. Literary critic Meena Alexander illustrates this fear of colonialism via language choice declaring, “Language has of course been an immensely controversial issue for Indian writers, the colonial trappings of English, when raised to consciousness, impossible to evade” (368).

Despite this viewpoint, Desai’s association with and eventual choice of English as her medium for expression seems less of a means to make a political statement and merely the consequence of a series of circumstances. These circumstances include a mixed heritage of Bengali and German, and an extensive education conducted in English. Desai has continually contended that English was simply the first language she was taught and thus became the obvious medium through which she expressed her thoughts in writing. Desai remarks in her essay “The Indian Writer’s Problems” that “according to the rules laid down by critics, I ought to be writing half my work in Bengali and the other half in German. As it happens, I have never written a word in either language. Possibly I found English to be a suitable link language, a compromise. But I can state definitely that I did not choose English in a deliberate and conscious act” (7). She further goes on to explain that “By writing novels that have been catalogued by critics as psychological, and that are purely subjective, I have been left free to employ, simply, the language of the interior” (9).

Like Anita Myles, I agree that there is no conclusive way Indian motherhood can be explained or defined, due to its immense complexity. Furthermore, defining Indian motherhood as only an oppressive construct or, in contrast, only an empowering construct, is not helpful for doing nuanced research or for understanding the actual lived reality of Indian mothers. Through the fiction of Anita Desai and specifically the three novels this project focused on, one is able to see how motherhood functions in Indian society and what informs its construction but also how difficult it is to speak of motherhood in generalities. Completing the research necessary to this project also reified the belief that there cannot be an overarching category of women or mother. Even in similar contexts or situations there are different histories, ideologies, mythical constructions and actual lived experiences. In order to understand Indian motherhood and have the ability to both critique its failings and celebrate its successes, one cannot merely ascribe characteristics to all Indian women or even all Indian mothers, and must explore the complex, often contradictory realm of Indian motherhood. This type of research is also necessary to avoid homogenization and essentialism, especially for those outside of the context of Indian society. In conclusion, this paper has operated

as an exploration of Indian motherhood, which sought to dispel essentialist misrepresentations and truly understand the societal role of mother and it has successfully portrayed the both the intricacy and heterogeneity of the ideological construct of Indian motherhood.

Works Cited

1. Desai, Anita. "A Secret Connivance." *The Times Literary Supplement* 14-20 September 1990: 972, 976. Print.
2. Desai, Anita---. *Clear Light of Day*. London: Vintage, 2001. Print.
3. Desai, Anita. *Fasting, Feasting*. New York: Houghton Mifflin, 2000. Print.
4. Desai, Anita. *Fire on the Mountain*. New York: Harper & Row, 1977. Print.
5. Dhawan, R. K---. "The Indian Writer's Problems." *Indian Women Novelists*. Ed. R.K. Dhawan. Vol. 2. New Delhi: Prestige, 1991. (7-10). Print.
6. Dhawan, R.K. "Introduction: Indian Women Novelists." *Indian Women Novelists*. Ed. R.K. Dhawan. Vol. 1. New Delhi: Prestige, 1991. (7-26). Print.
7. Gupta, Santosh. "Women Writing About Women: Feminist Perspective in Indian Women's Novel in English." *Women about Women in Indian Literature in English*. Ed. Ram S. Singh and Charu S. Singh. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1998. (73-90). Print.
8. Myles, Anita. *Feminism and the Post-Modern Indian Women Novelist in English*. New Delhi: Sarup & Son, 2006. Print.